

RESEARCH REPORT

Export Dynamics of Punjab

Performance, Potential, and Pathways

October 2025

PANJ

Policy Advisory and
Network for Joint Progress

PANJ

*Policy Advisory and
Network for Joint Progress*

Table of contents

List of abbreviations	1
List of tables and figures	2
Overview: Why exports matter?	3
Placing Punjab in national exports	4
Data story	6
Punjab's export share	6
Where is Punjab exporting to?	7
What is Punjab exporting?	8
Which districts are the top players?	17
Which are the major dry ports for agricultural exports?	25
Special column: Attari Integrated Checkpost	29
Conclusion	30
References	31

Authors and attribution

Deepratan Singh Khara, Anmol Rattan Singh, Harleen Gill, Agastya Shukla, and Sehaj Singh

Khara, D.S., et al., *Export Dynamics of Punjab*, PANJ Foundation, October 2025; DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17272338](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17272338)

Copyright

This research report has been prepared in good faith on the basis of information available at the date of publication. Copyright: PANJ Foundation 2025.

List of abbreviations

APEDA	Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CFS	Container Freight Station
EPI	Export Preparedness Index
EV	Electric Vehicle
GCC	Global Capability Centre
GI	Geographical Indicator
GRFL	Gateway Rail Freight Limited
ICD	Inland Container Depots
IT/ITes	Information Technology / Information Technology Enabled Services
NIRYAT	National Import-Export Record for Yearly Analysis of Trade, Government of India
NLP	National Logistics Policy, 2022
NTB	Non-Tariff Barriers
MRL	Maximum Residue Levels
PLIL	Punjab Logistics Infrastructure Limited
SAS Nagar	Sahibzada Ajit Singh Nagar
SBS Nagar	Shaheed Bhagat Singh Nagar
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures
STPI	Software Technology Parks of India
USD	United States Dollar
WTO	World Trade Organization

List of figures

Figure 1: Punjab's total exports between 2017-2024 (in USD million and % share in national exports)
Figure 2: Punjab's flow of exports (top 10 countries) in 2023-24
Figure 3: Punjab's flow of exports (top 10 countries) in 2024-25
Figure 4: Composition of commodity share in Punjab's exports
Figure 5: CAGR of different sub-commodities, Punjab (2017-2024)
Figure 6: Year-on-year % change in Punjab's IT exports(2017-2024)
Figure 7: District-wise share of exports

List of tables

Table 1: Share of major commodities in Punjab's exports and national exports
Table 2: Rank of Punjab vis-a-vis top three leading states
Table 3: IT exports by STPI units in Punjab
Table 4: District-wise top 3 products and their share in the district's exports
Table 5: District wise average product share (2021-24)
Table 6: District-wise top products
Table 7: Exporting points in Punjab

Overview

Why exports matter?

Exports have historically been acknowledged as one of the most powerful drivers of economic growth. Classical trade theorists such as David Ricardo (2004) emphasised comparative advantage, while the Heckscher–Ohlin framework highlighted how regions with abundant factors of production could specialise and trade for mutual benefit (Horvat, 1999). With the advent of new trade theories, scholars like Paul Krugman have underscored the importance of economies of scale, product differentiation, and the agglomeration of industries in shaping trade patterns (Chandra, 2022).

In recent years, firm-level empirical studies have highlighted the concept of learning by exporting. This is explained as when firms enter export markets, they gain exposure to greater competition, advanced technologies, improved management practices, and higher quality standards, which in turn enhance their productivity. Evidence consistently shows that participation in international markets pushes firms to meet stricter buyer demands, upgrade their processes, and move up the quality ladder, thereby illustrating learning by exporting in practice. The World Bank’s World Development Report 2020 also shows evidence in favour of how trade and “production sharing” raise productivity, wages, and technology adoption (World Bank, 2020).

Rising exports enable a country to increase imports, specifically capital goods, which are critical enablers of economic growth. By leveraging the international division of labour, countries can procure goods efficiently and enhance industrial productivity. Export growth directs investment toward sectors with comparative advantage that fosters specialisation, economies of scale, and operational efficiency. A dynamic export sector generates secondary benefits as well. A major chunk of it includes higher investment, consumption, and technology transfer. Profitable exports attract domestic and foreign investment and stimulate ancillary industries that support the main export sector. In many less-developed countries, exports are the primary driver of overall economic activity; slow export growth correlates with slower general economic growth.

Placing Punjab in national exports

At the global level, countries that sustained export growth also transformed structurally. India's story is increasingly consistent with that trajectory. Despite turbulent global conditions, India posted its highest-ever merchandise exports of about USD 451.1 billion in FY 2022–23. Within that, electronics emerged as a breakout category, rising sharply in recent years as policy nudges and scale manufacturing took hold ([NIRYAT portal](#), [Government of India](#)).

India's trajectory of export expansion exhibits considerable spatial heterogeneity. Coastal states such as Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Karnataka continue to consolidate their advantage by capitalising on maritime infrastructure and well-developed industrial ecosystems. However, landlocked states, recognising the strategic importance of export-led growth, are progressively narrowing this gap. By investing in Inland Container Depots (ICDs), enhancing freight connectivity, and fostering cluster-based manufacturing, these states are effectively mitigating the structural constraints associated with the absence of ports. This shift is substantiated by findings from NITI Aayog's Export Preparedness [Index](#) (EPI), which records notable improvements in the export performance of all states and UT's. The EPI provides a comprehensive benchmarking framework, assessing states across four pillars: Policy, Business Ecosystem, Export Ecosystem, and Export Performance—through a set of 56 indicators.

Situated within this national context, Punjab presents a particularly compelling case. Long regarded as India's breadbasket, the state has earned global recognition for its basmati rice exports. Annual reports and datasets from the Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority ([APEDA](#)) not only affirm India's leadership in basmati exports but also highlight Punjab's central role in sustaining this value chain. Beyond agriculture, industrial clusters of Punjab have carved out distinctive competitive niches: Ludhiana, Jalandhar, Kapurthala, and Hoshiarpur are recognised for their production of hand tools, fasteners, bicycles, and agricultural machinery, while S.A.S. Nagar has emerged as a hub for pharmaceuticals and IT/ITeS.

The geographical position of Punjab makes an even more compelling case for the study of its exports and the diversification of products. Being landlocked, the state had to primarily rely on a dense network of ICDs. As a result, an ICD ecosystem has emerged at Ludhiana, Jalandhar, Amritsar, Bathinda relying on multimodal corridors to reach premier ports including the Jawaharlal Nehru Port Authority in Mumbai and Mundra in Gujarat. The approach of creating a strong network of ICDs and channels of multimodal corridors is also in alignment with the National Logistics Policy (NLP) [2022](#), which aims to integrate logistics

systems and push costs toward global benchmarks through digital platforms and coordinated infrastructure.

Crucially, rising export readiness of Punjab now shows up in subsequent EPI numbers. In 2020, Punjab began from a relatively modest base of overall rank 18. In 2021, Punjab climbed sharply to an overall rank of 8th and among the best landlocked performers. In 2022, Punjab scored 58.95 and ranked 10th nationally and the fourth best landlocked state.

The performance of Punjab on the EPI highlights a productive tension between preparedness and outcomes. Export readiness has advanced more rapidly than realised export performance, with the state's export basket still dominated by agri-food products and mid-level engineering. This contrasts with India achieving a national record in 2022–23, led by fast-growing sectors such as electronics, specialty chemicals, and pharmaceuticals. The divergence indicates both opportunity and vulnerability. A strong base in basmati rice and medium-scale manufacturing provides stability, yet dependence on these sectors limits alignment with shifting global demand. A renewed export strategy therefore calls for consolidation of existing strengths, diversification into emerging sectors, and investment in logistics, infrastructure, and innovation to translate potential into broad-based and sustainable growth.

This report presents an analysis of export performance and related trends in Punjab. The study is organised around six guiding questions: (i) what is the position of Punjab in the national export share?; (ii) which are the principal export destinations?; (iii) what commodities are being exported?; (iv) how is export activity distributed across districts?; (v) which dry ports play a significant role in agricultural exports?; and (vi) what is the strategic importance of the Attari Integrated Checkpost?

Each section combines a data-driven narrative with recommendations and potential approaches for enabling Punjab to emerge as a frontrunner in exports. By employing quantitative evidence, tracing key patterns, and integrating sectoral, geographical, and policy perspectives, the report develops an understanding of the export landscape of Punjab and sets out strategic measures aimed at strengthening the state's overall export performance. The report assumes particular relevance at the current juncture as Punjab aims to diversify the export base in line with shifting global trade dynamics following the tariff measures initiated by the West, while also seeking to leverage new policy initiatives under India's foreign trade framework. The insights generated are therefore essential for evidence-based decision-making and the formulation of strategies that enhance competitiveness and resilience in external trade.

Data story

Punjab's export share

Data indicates that exports from Punjab have yet to experience a significant growth spurt. Figure 1 illustrates this through two interrelated but distinct indicators: (a) merchandise export value in million US dollars (bars); (b) percentage share in India's total merchandise exports (line). Together, these indicators capture both overall export performance over time and relative contribution to the country's total exports.

Figure 1: Punjab's total exports between 2017-2024 (in USD billion and % share in national exports)

Source: [NIRYAT portal](#), [Government of India](#)

In nominal USD terms, exports from Punjab increased from 5.79 billion in 2017–18 to 6.74 billion in 2023–24. The trend exhibits two distinct phases, with a slowdown in 2019–20 followed by a strong rebound in 2021–22, reaching the highest level recorded after the COVID period. During 2022–24, export growth moderated slightly before stabilising. These fluctuations mirror global patterns influenced by disruptions in demand and supply chains during the pandemic, followed by normalisation in freight and the clearance of pent-up orders transported through ICDs. The chart further indicates a decline in the share of Punjab in India's merchandise exports, from 1.9 percent in 2017–18 to 1.5 percent in 2023–24. The slight increase observed in 2020 reflects a denominator effect, arising from the fact that India's total exports

contracted more sharply than exports from Punjab during that year, resulting in a temporary relative uplift in the state's contribution.

However, this trend did not persist in subsequent years. As India's total exports expanded, the share of Punjab declined despite a recovery in the state's own export growth. The divergence in growth rates reflects differences in the composition of exports: national growth was largely driven by merchandise categories such as petroleum products, electronics, and specialty chemicals, whereas growth in Punjab was primarily concentrated in existing sectors. Between 2017–18 and 2023–24, Punjab ranked 14th to 15th nationally in terms of export value, with exports growing at an a CAGR of 2.6 percent ([NIRYAT portal](#), [Government of India](#)).

Where is Punjab exporting to?

A significant concentration of exports is observed in a limited number of markets, with ten countries collectively accounting for 51.6 percent of total exports from Punjab. These key destinations include the United States of America (USA), United Arab Emirates (UAE), Bangladesh, Saudi Arabia, United Kingdom (UK), Germany, China, Brazil, Turkey, and Australia ([FIEO](#), 2024). In 2023–24, the USA emerged as the principal market, absorbing 15.5 percent of total exports, reflecting established trade linkages and the strategic importance of North American demand in shaping the state's external trade patterns (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2: Punjab's flow of exports (top 10 countries) in 2023-24

Source: [FIEO state-wise export data 2023-24](#)

The United States remained the leading export destination in 2024–25, although its share declined to 12.1 percent (*Figure 3*). During the same period, Saudi Arabia's share increased from 5.9 percent to 9.5 percent, moving it to the second position, while the United Kingdom

emerged as the third-largest export destination. These shifts underscore evolving global demand patterns and reinforce the importance of strategic market diversification to sustain and expand the state’s export presence.

High concentration of exports in a limited number of markets presents a notable risk, as even minor changes in these economies can produce significant fluctuations in export performance from Punjab. This vulnerability has become particularly evident following recently imposed tariffs by the United States. Given that the US remains the largest export destination, exporters from the state are already experiencing impacts. Reports already indicate mounting challenges for basmati rice and auto component sectors, which constitute two of the major export categories from Punjab.

Figure 3: Punjab’s flow of exports (top 10 countries) in 2024-25

Source: [FIEO state-wise export data 2024-25](#)

What is Punjab exporting?

Punjab exhibits a relatively narrow range of export commodities compared with other states, and the composition of exports has remained largely stable over time. This limited diversification highlights a structural feature of the state trade profile, which relies heavily on a few key sectors. Table 1 presents the major commodities exported from Punjab, showing their share in (a) total exports from the state, and (b) India’s total exports of the corresponding commodity. The table not only illustrates concentration within specific sectors but also provides a comparative perspective on the state contribution to national trade in each

commodity, offering insight into both strengths and potential vulnerabilities in the export portfolio.

Table 1: Share of major commodities in Punjab's exports and national exports

		2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
Agriculture	Share in state's total export	22.63	21.71	20.63	12.82	17.58	18.14
	Share in India's total export	5.38	5.30	4.06	3.13	3.60	3.68
Chemicals & Allied Products	Share in state's total export	4.84	4.68	4.58	4.36	4.72	4.50
	Share in India's total export	0.43	0.41	0.42	0.27	0.23	0.24
Drugs & Pharmaceuticals	Share in state's total export	6.76	7.38	8.81	6.63	7.90	7.47
	Share in India's total export	2.14	2.00	1.91	1.91	2.06	1.81
Electronic Goods	Share in state's total export	0.42	1.15	0.88	1.00	1.40	1.57
	Share in India's total export	0.29	0.55	0.42	0.45	0.39	0.36
Engineering Goods	Share in state's total export	31.92	33.75	36.12	40.91	40.44	41.15
	Share in India's total export	2.35	2.45	2.53	2.59	2.51	2.54
Gems & Jewellery	Share in state's total export	0.18	0.17	0.04	0.31	0.28	0.47
	Share in India's total export	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.06	0.05	0.10
Leather & Leather Manufactures	Share in state's total export	0.68	0.69	0.67	0.73	0.60	0.54
	Share in India's total export	0.80	0.83	1.07	1.18	0.83	0.86
Textiles	Share in state's total export	28.47	26.05	24.00	28.96	21.67	20.97
	Share in India's total export	4.78	4.32	4.32	4.97	4.04	4.11
Others	Share in state's total export	4.09	4.43	4.26	4.27	5.43	5.19
	Share in India's total export	1.39	1.49	1.20	1.07	1.27	1.47

Source: [NIRYAT portal](#), Government of India

Within the export portfolio of Punjab, engineering goods represent the most prominent sector, reflecting both industrial capacity and trade specialisation. The share of this commodity group in total exports from the state increased markedly from 31.9 percent in 2018–19 to 41.2 percent in 2023–24, highlighting a growing reliance on medium-scale manufacturing for export growth (*Figure 4*). This category includes products such as hand tools, agricultural machinery, and fasteners, which collectively underpin the industrial export base and demonstrate the state’s ability to cater to specialised global demand. However, despite its significance within the state, the contribution to India’s total exports of engineering goods remains limited. Between 2018–19 and 2023–24, the state share in national exports of this category rose only marginally from 2.4 percent to 2.5 percent, revealing a strong internal specialisation but a modest national footprint. This contrast underscores both the potential and constraints of industrial export strategy of Punjab, suggesting opportunities for scaling up production, upgrading technology, and expanding market reach to translate sectoral strength into greater national and global competitiveness.

Textile exports constitute the second most significant component of the Punjab export portfolio, although their relative contribution has gradually declined over time. Between 2018–19 and 2023–24, the share of textile exports in total exports from the state decreased from 28.5 percent to 20.9 percent, reflecting a weakening of the sector contribution to overall trade. The decline in textile exports can be attributed to several factors, including increasing global competition, rising input costs, and challenges in meeting quality and compliance standards in international markets. Despite this slowdown, textiles continue to form an important part of the state industrial base, supporting employment, small-scale manufacturing clusters, and traditional production skills.

Agriculture-related exports constitute the third most significant category in the export composition of Punjab. However, these exports do not demonstrate a sustained growth trajectory. Between 2018–19 and 2021–22, the share of agricultural exports in total exports from the state declined sharply from 22.6 percent to 12.8 percent, representing a drop of nearly 10 percentage points. During this period, agricultural exports followed a V-shaped pattern, falling to 12.8 percent in 2021–22 before recovering to 18.1 percent in 2023–24. Several factors potentially explain this volatility. First, agricultural exports remain highly sensitive to natural and climatic variations, resulting in unpredictable production outcomes. Second, recent years have seen increased scrutiny through non-tariff barriers (NTBs), which disproportionately affect agriculture-related exports from Punjab. Countries including the United States, the European Union, and Middle Eastern nations enforce WTO-sanctioned sanitary and

phytosanitary measures (SPS) and impose limits on pesticide maximum residue levels (MRLs), creating additional compliance challenges (Asian Development Bank, 2020). Despite these constraints, early signs of recovery indicate resilience in the sector and potential for further growth if structural and regulatory challenges are addressed.

Figure 4: Composition of commodity share in Punjab's exports

Source: *NIRYAT portal, Government of India*

Emerging sectors offer significant potential to reshape the export landscape of Punjab, yet current performance indicates underutilised opportunities. Relative underperformance in high-growth areas such as electronics and chemicals is a notable concern. Between 2018–19 and 2023–24, the share of electronics in total exports from the state increased only from 0.4 percent to 1.6 percent, reflecting slow integration into a rapidly expanding global market. Similarly, the share of chemical exports in national total exports declined slightly, from 4.8 percent to 4.5 percent over the same period, highlighting limited competitiveness and scope for expansion in this high-value sector.

Sub-commodities

A sub-commodity perspective provides a deeper understanding of the specific products that constitute Punjab exports. Figure 5 presents the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of different sub-commodities, capturing the average annual rate of change in export values between 2017–18 and 2023–24. Products with positive CAGR indicate a growing export base over the reference period, highlighting emerging strengths and diversification.

Figure 5: CAGR of different sub-commodities, Punjab (2017-2024)

Source: Calculated using data from [NIRYAT portal](#), Government of India

The results reveal a highly uneven performance across sectors. Electronic goods recorded the highest CAGR of 35.5 percent, reflecting a gradual transition toward higher-value, technology-oriented exports. Other notable gainers include other cereals (29.4 percent), gems and jewellery (25.2 percent), and handicrafts excluding carpets (19.6 percent), suggesting increasing competitiveness in non-traditional export sectors. Moderate growth in engineering goods, processed food items, and organic and inorganic chemicals further demonstrates the resilience of the industrial base and potential for deeper integration with national and global value chains.

In contrast, several commodities exhibit negative CAGR values, indicating sustained decline in export performance. The sharpest contractions occur in cashew (-31.9 percent), petroleum products (-23.4 percent), and jute manufacturing (-19.9 percent), likely reflecting global price volatility, supply disruptions, and shifts in trade demand. Traditional agricultural exports such as rice (-3.5 percent) and spices (-13 percent) also registered negative growth, potentially due to tightening of non-tariff barriers, including sanitary and phytosanitary measures and pesticide residue limits enforced by importing countries. Overall, the analysis underscores a structural shift in Punjab export composition, where industrial and technology-based products are emerging as key growth drivers, while agricultural and resource-dependent sectors experience stagnation or decline.

These trends provide a basis for strategic interventions. Punjab export activity is shifting toward higher-value manufacturing, with strong momentum in electronics and engineering goods. Policy support in supplier development, testing, certification, and export finance is crucial to strengthen these clusters. Negative growth in traditional agricultural exports underscores the need for processed product development, GI-based branding, traceability, and modern milling and packaging. Textiles require strategic upgrading through textile parks, design studios, lean manufacturing, and end-to-end investment ecosystems. Niche sectors such as handicrafts and gems offer diversification opportunities and can scale through digital marketing, logistics, and design support. Base effects caution against overemphasis on high-growth rates from small starting values; absolute economic significance and employment impact should guide prioritisation. Overall, sustained export growth depends on consolidating strong sectors, addressing weaknesses in textiles and agricultural quality systems, and scaling emerging categories through targeted cluster and capability interventions.

Between 2017–18 and 2023–24 the export profile of Punjab reflects a clear pattern of sectoral unevenness, balancing its agro-based strength with a relatively limited industrial diversification. Across major export segments—Meat, Dairy and Poultry; Man-Made Yarn; Cotton; Rice; and Readymade Garments—Punjab retains visibility but demonstrates varying degrees of competitiveness and dynamism.

In the Meat, Dairy and Poultry segment, Punjab consistently ranks third nationally, yet its share has gradually declined from 7.3 percent in 2017–18 to 4.8 percent in 2023–24. This steady fall indicates a loss of export intensity, even as the sector continues to provide livelihoods and domestic supply strength. The decline is linked to limited scale in export-oriented processing, stringent quality compliance norms, and logistical challenges compared with Uttar Pradesh,

Table 2: Rank of Punjab vis-a-vis top three leading states

Year	Meat, Dairy and Poultry			Man Made Yarn			Cotton			Rice			Readymade garment		
	Rank	State	Share (%)	Rank	State	Share (%)	Rank	State	Share (%)	Rank	State	Share (%)	Rank	State	Share (%)
2017-18	1	Uttar Pradesh	51.38	1	Gujarat	24.22	1	Gujarat	26.63	1	Haryana	32.27	1	Tamil Nadu	27.15
	2	Maharashtra	21.61	2	Maharashtra	21.12	2	Tamil Nadu	18.45	2	Punjab	14.44	2	Delhi	16.79
	3	Punjab	7.33	3	Daman & Diu	15.12	3	Maharashtra	13.39	3	West Bengal	7.47	3	Karnataka	12.19
	-	-	-	8	Punjab	3.11	4	Punjab	9.15	-	-	-	7	Punjab	4.25
2018-19	1	Uttar Pradesh	53.57	1	Gujarat	25.98	1	Gujarat	26.87	1	Haryana	31.64	1	Tamil Nadu	29.38
	2	Maharashtra	19.39%	2	Maharashtra	19.10	2	Tamil Nadu	17.92	2	Gujarat	14.52	2	Delhi	12.63
	3	Punjab	6.44	3	Daman & Diu	15.86	3	Maharashtra	14.29	3	Punjab	12.62	3	Karnataka	12.28
	-	-	-	7	Punjab	3.26	4	Punjab	8.94	-	-	-	7	Punjab	3.33
2019-20	1	Uttar Pradesh	51.79	1	Gujarat	25.19	1	Gujarat	26.78	1	Haryana	38.26	1	Tamil Nadu	29.81
	2	Maharashtra	23.71	2	Maharashtra	18.25	2	Tamil Nadu	18.37	2	Punjab	14.16	2	Karnataka	12.25
	3	Punjab	5.56	3	Daman & Diu	14.58	3	Maharashtra	15.07	3	Gujarat	10.65	3	Uttar Pradesh	12.24
	-	-	-	10	Punjab	2.68	4	Punjab	7.70%	-	-	-	7	Punjab	3.53
2020-21	1	Uttar Pradesh	53.65	1	Gujarat	26.18	1	Gujarat	26.59	1	Haryana	27.40	1	Tamil Nadu	32.27
	2	Maharashtra	20.70	2	Maharashtra	17.93	2	Tamil Nadu	18.51	2	Gujarat	11.27	2	Uttar Pradesh	11.81
	3	Bihar	6.64	3	Daman & Diu	13.64	3	Maharashtra	15.11	3	Andhra Pradesh	8.85	3	Delhi	11.49
	4	Punjab	5.86	8	Punjab	3.38	5	Punjab	7.21	4	Punjab	8.84	7	Punjab	3.41
2021-22	1	Uttar Pradesh	50.28	1	Gujarat	25.87	1	Gujarat	27.03	1	Haryana	23.25	1	Tamil Nadu	33.11
	2	Maharashtra	22.97	2	Maharashtra	16.30	2	Tamil Nadu	18.53	2	Gujarat	15.31	2	Uttar Pradesh	12.54
	3	Punjab	5.07	3	Daman & Diu	16.19	3	Maharashtra	12.73	3	Chhattisgarh	12.06	3	Haryana	12.51
	-	-	-	8	Punjab	3.51	4	Punjab	8.33	7	Punjab	6.02	7	Punjab	3.44
2022-23	1	Uttar Pradesh	48.90	1	Gujarat	26.95	1	Gujarat	25.21	1	Haryana	25.90	1	Tamil Nadu	32.95
	2	Maharashtra	23.16	2	Maharashtra	18.80	2	Tamil Nadu	20.73	2	Gujarat	16.03	2	Uttar Pradesh	14.09
	3	Punjab	5.16	3	Daman & Diu	12.23	3	Maharashtra	13.19	3	Chhattisgarh	10.43	3	Karnataka	13.64
	-	-	-	9	Punjab	3.16	6	Punjab	6.68	6	Punjab	7.54	7	Punjab	3.21
2023-24	1	Uttar Pradesh	51.54	1	Gujarat	26.99	1	Gujarat	28.76	1	Haryana	31.70	1	Tamil Nadu	32.27
	2	Maharashtra	20.60	2	Maharashtra	18.71	2	Tamil Nadu	17.66	2	Gujarat	14.29	2	Uttar Pradesh	14.08
	3	Punjab	4.79	3	Rajasthan	11.39	3	Maharashtra	12.76	3	Andhra Pradesh	8.35	3	Karnataka	13.62
	-	-	-	8	Punjab	3.84	6	Punjab	6.66	4	Punjab	8.28	7	Punjab	2.93

Source: NIRYAT portal, Government of India

which dominates over half of India's exports in this category. The strong livestock base of the Punjab remains underutilised in terms of value-added meat and dairy exports, pointing toward untapped agribusiness potential.

Punjab's role in man-made yarn exports is minimal, with its share hovering between 3 percent and 3.8 percent, placing it between 7th and 10th rank nationally. The dominance of Gujarat and Maharashtra, supported by the western industrial corridor's dense synthetic textile clusters, highlights Punjab's lag in technological adaptation to synthetic fiber manufacturing. Despite Ludhiana's textile reputation, Punjab's export base remains cotton-centric rather than synthetic, reflecting industrial path dependency and the need for modernisation and diversification toward global demand trends.

In cotton exports, Punjab consistently features among the top five states, contributing around 6 to 9 percent. This steady yet moderate presence underscores its strong agricultural foundation in cotton cultivation, particularly in southern districts like Bathinda and Mansa. However, compared to Gujarat's large-scale integrated textile processing and export infrastructure, Punjab's cotton sector remains agro-driven rather than industrially diversified, limiting its value capture in the textile export chain.

The state's export trajectory in rice, particularly basmati rice, exhibits both decline and recovery. Its share fell from 14.2 percent in 2019–20 to 6 percent in 2021–22, reflecting challenges such as declining water tables, yield variability, and global price volatility. However, by 2023–24, Punjab's share rose again to 8.3 percent, indicating a partial rebound driven by improved processing infrastructure, quality differentiation, and favourable international demand. Although Haryana has overtaken Punjab as the national leader, Punjab remains an integral part of India's basmati export belt, anchoring the country's agro-export identity.

In terms of readymade garments, the share remains stable around 3 to 4 percent. While Ludhiana is a major domestic knitwear hub, much of its production caters to internal markets, not exports. This limited international integration reflects low global branding, dependence on seasonal demand, and a fragmented small-scale industrial structure. To strengthen its position, Punjab needs export-oriented scaling, adoption of sustainable textile technologies, and global supply chain linkages to match the export dynamism of Tamil Nadu and Karnataka.

Punjab's IT exports

Table 3: IT exports by STPI units in Punjab

Year	Exports (USD million)
2017-18	50.67
2018-19	70.94
2019-20	67.30
2020-21	97.97
2021-22	134.71
2022-23	262.09
2023-24	309.68

Source: [Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology](#)

Table 3 highlights the trend in IT exports from STPI units in Punjab over the period 2017-18 to 2023-24. The data shows a strong upward trajectory, with exports rising from USD 50.67 million in 2017-18 to USD 309.68 million in 2023-24, reflecting more than a six-fold increase over six years. This growth indicates the gradual emergence of Punjab as a contributor to India's IT export ecosystem, albeit from a relatively small base.

But, the growth of IT exports in Punjab has not been linear, instead data shows the emergence of distinct phases.

Figure 6: Year-on-year % change in Punjab's IT exports (2017-2024)

Source: [Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology](#)

A sharp jump between 2017-18 to 2018-19 when the year-on-year (YoY) growth reveals fluctuations, highlighting both volatility and acceleration phases. After a slight decline of 3.4 percent in 2018-19, exports rebounded with a 13.9 percent increase in 2019-20, followed by

another moderate increase of 13.7 percent in 2020-21. A sharper growth of 40 percent occurred in 2021–22, reflecting stronger market demand and possibly the expansion of STPI units and service offerings. The surge continued with a 45.5 percent increase in 2022–23 and 17.9 percent growth in 2023–24, reaching USD 309.68 million. This pattern underscores both resilience and the increasing maturity of IT services in Punjab, including software development, BPO services, and digital solutions.

Overall, the data suggests that IT exports in Punjab are on a robust growth path, with increasing contribution to the state’s export basket. The significant acceleration in recent years points to the potential for further expansion, provided that supportive measures such as infrastructure enhancement, skilled workforce development, and export facilitation continue to strengthen the IT sector. This includes backing product and SaaS exporters with bridge funding initiatives, state facilitated global go-to-market assistance, and soft landing programmes in key markets. Moreover, the state would benefit further from ‘decentralising’ the centres for IT exports. S.A.S Nagar was alone responsible for **75 percent** of the state’s IT exports in FY 2022-23. The district’s expanding base of IT sector (growth of **14 percent** in past five years) also indicates its readiness for becoming a Global Capability Center (GCC) hub. While this is a positive indicator on the capacity of S.A.S Nagar, Punjab needs more IT exporting districts to expand its base.

Which districts are the top players?

The district-wise distribution of Punjab exports reveals a pronounced spatial concentration, with activity clustered primarily in a few industrial and commercial centres. The top tier is dominated by Ludhiana, contributing 38.9 percent in 2021–22 and moderating slightly to 36.1 percent in 2023–24, accounting for over one-third of total exports. S.A.S. Nagar holds the second position with a stable double-digit share of 12.8-13.4 percent, driven by IT/ITeS, pharmaceuticals, and electronics. Jalandhar follows closely, contributing around 12 percent across the three years, reflecting sustained strength in sports goods, hand tools, light engineering, and leather-based manufacturing. Collectively, these three districts account for approximately 62-64 percent of total exports, underscoring the critical role of established industrial hubs in shaping overall export performance.

A second tier of mid-performing districts includes Amritsar, Hoshiarpur, Patiala, Sangrur, Bathinda, and S.B.S. Nagar, which together contributed roughly 18–20 percent. The share of Amritsar increased from 5.6 to 6.4 percent, driven by basmati rice, food processing, and light manufacturing. Hoshiarpur rose from 5.9 to 6.1 percent, reflecting diversification in

engineering and agro-processing units. Patiala remained relatively stable, ranging from 3.7 to 3.4 percent, underpinned by small-scale engineering and agro-based industries. Sangrur declined slightly from 3.6 to 2.9 percent, while Bathinda fell from 3.2 to 2.6 percent, largely due to weakness in petroleum-linked and agro-processed exports. S.B.S. Nagar maintained a small but steady contribution, increasing marginally from 2.5 to 2.6 percent, reflecting a stable local industrial base.

Figure 7: District-wise share of exports

Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India

A third group of emerging but smaller contributors includes Barnala (from 3.8 percent to 2.6 percent), Kapurthala (from 2.2 percent to 2.4 percent), and Firozpur (from 1.4 percent to 2.1 percent), each showing either moderate decline or improvement. Moga exhibited upward momentum, rising from 0.9 to 1.9 percent, likely driven by growth in food processing and dairy exports, while Fazilka witnessed fluctuating levels of 0.8 percent to 1.1 percent, reflecting gradual integration into the state’s export ecosystem.

Finally, a long tail of low-share districts continued to contribute less than 1 percent each, including Faridkot, Fatehgarh Sahib, Gurdaspur, Mansa, Pathankot, Rupnagar, Sri Muktsar Sahib, and Tarn Taran. Among these, Rupnagar (from 0.2 percent to 0.4 percent) and Tarn Taran (from 1.1 percent to 2.3 percent) exhibited small but noteworthy improvements, whereas Gurdaspur and Mansa remained largely stagnant. Collectively, these districts highlight the structural imbalance and industrial concentration in Punjab, where export potential remains underutilised due to infrastructure gaps, weak industrial ecosystems, and limited connectivity.

Table 4: District-wise top 3 products and their share in the district's exports

District	Year	1	2	3
Amritsar	2021-22	Basmati Rice (46.9%)	Other medicament containing (4.3%)	Shawls/mufflers of manmade fibre (2.8%)
	2022-23	Basmati Rice (53.2%)	Broken rice (4.8%)	Jewellery of gold set (2.6%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (59.5%)	Shawls,scarves,mufflers etc of synthetic fibres (2.2%)	Other medicine put up for retail sale N.E.S (1.8%)
Barnala	2021-22	Linen (47.9%)	Ibuprofen (11.1%)	Cotton (10.1%)
	2022-23	Linen (48.4%)	Ibuprofen (17.7%)	Cotton (4.8%)
	2023-24	Linen (42.2%)	Ibuprofen (22.6%)	Cotton (6.3%)
Bathinda	2021-22	Cotton ¹ (35.0%)	Cotton ² (30.3%)	Polyester yarn (5.7%)
	2022-23	Cotton ¹ (31.9%)	Cotton ² (28.8%)	Cotton ³ (6.7%)
	2023-24	Cotton ¹ (32.2%)	Cotton ² (26.6%)	Cotton ³ (5.9%)
Faridkot	2021-22	Basmati rice (37.9%)	Rice (17.0%)	Harvesting machines (5.2%)
	2022-23	Basmati rice (41.4%)	Rice (parboiled) (17.8%)	Machinery (6.5%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (51.6%)	Rice (21.9%)	Cotton (7.6%)
Fatehgarh S.	2021-22	Others (16.8%)	Spring steel (8.9%)	Rolling mill rolls (6.6%)
	2022-23	Rolling mill parts (12.2%)	Biscuits (10.6%)	Others (8.5%)
	2023-24	Rolling mill parts (12.0%)	Biscuits (9.4%)	Baby garments (5.7%)
Fazilka	2021-22	Basmati rice (70.2%)	Oranges (21.8%)	Cotton (1.3%)
	2022-23	Basmati rice (96.6%)	Rice (1.2%)	Rice (parboiled) (0.9%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (99.0%)	Sugar (0.4%)	Rice (parboiled) (0.3%)
Firozpur	2021-22	Basmati rice (86.3%)	Rice (5.1%)	Chana (1.5%)
	2022-23	Basmati rice (84.8%)	Rice (parboiled) (7.0%)	Rice (4.5%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (94.0%)	Rice (parboiled) (3.9%)	Chana (0.9%)
Gurdaspur	2021-22	Basmati rice (14.9%)	Jewellery of gold set (17.1%)	Other spirit of undenatured alcohol (16.85%)
	2022-23	Other spirit of undenatured alcohol (37.9%)	Basmati rice (33.3%)	Jewellery of gold set (4.3%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (39.3%)	Other spirit of undenatured ethyl alcohol (16.8%)	Cane molasses resulting from extraction/refining of sugar (7.3%)

¹ GREY 52052410

² GREY 52052310

³ GREY 52052210

District	Year	1	2	3
Hoshiarpur	2021-22	Tractors (37-75 kw) (40.8%)	Small tractors (17.5%)	Medium tractors (14.3%)
	2022-23	Tractors (37-75 kw) (38.3%)	Small tractors (22.3%)	Medium tractors (12.2%)
	2023-24	Other tractors (44.7%)	Other tractors (19.2%)	Other tractors (12.7%)
Jalandhar	2021-22	Spanners (12.0%)	Scaffolding props (7.5%)	Hand tools (4.1%)
	2022-23	Spanners (10.3%)	Scaffolding props (8.2%)	Basmati rice (4.1%)
	2023-24	Spanners (9.6%)	Scaffolding props (9.4%)	Basmati rice (6.2%)
Kapurthala	2021-22	Vehicle axles (39.2%)	Vehicle parts (27.0%)	Flour prep (7.0%)
	2022-23	Vehicle parts (57.1%)	Vehicle axles (12.8%)	Flour prep (8.0%)
	2023-24	Vehicle parts (73.9%)	Flour prep (5.9%)	Molasses (2.1%)
Ludhiana	2021-22	Vehicle parts (6.1%)	Cotton (5.3%)	Scaffolding props (3.9%)
	2022-23	Vehicle parts (6.2%)	Screws & bolts (4.2%)	Scaffolding props (4.0%)
	2023-24	Vehicle parts (6.5%)	Scaffolding props (5.0%)	Screws & bolts (3.4%)
Mansa	2021-22	Cotton ⁴ (22.4%)	Cotton ⁵ (16.3%)	Cotton ⁶ (8.5%)
	2022-23	Cotton ⁶ (29.2%)	Rolling mill rolls (16.8%)	Cotton ⁵ (10.4%)
	2023-24	Beams/channels (63.1%)	Cotton ⁵ (11.4%)	Rolling mill rolls (3.3%)
Moga	2021-22	Basmati rice (64.2%)	Rice (12.0%)	Infant food (5.1%)
	2022-23	Basmati rice (70.1%)	Rice (parboiled) (9.6%)	Rice (6.4%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (82.0%)	Rice (parboiled) (5.8%)	Dairy products (2.1%)
Muksar	2021-22	Cotton ⁵ (51.0%)	Cotton ⁷ (16.0%)	Cotton ⁴ (5.0%)
	2022-23	Cotton ⁵ (25.9%)	Medicines (21.4%)	Cotton ⁶ (17.8%)
	2023-24	Cotton ⁵ (17.1%)	Paper (16.1%)	Medicines (15.3%)
Pathankot	2021-22	Sewing Machines ⁸ (18.7%)	Sewing Machines ⁹ (16.9%)	Glucose solid (10.3%)
	2022-23	Sewing Machines ⁸ (17.9%)	Dresses of synthetic fibres (12.8%)	Kraft liner unbleached (7.3%)
	2023-24	Other articles for conveyance (56.88%)	Spirit of undenatured ethyl alcohol (31.1%)	Other mechanical shovels, excavators, shovel loaders (1.6%)
Patiala	2021-22	Meat (14.4%)	Sheets/strips (11.0%)	Cotton ¹⁰ (8.8%)
	2022-23	Honey (12.0%)	Batteries (11.2%)	Meat (7.6%)
	2023-24	Cotton ¹⁰ (8.9%)	Rubber pipes (7.0%)	Honey (6.5%)

⁴ GREY 52051210

⁵ GREY 52052310

⁶ GREY 52051310

⁷ GREY 52052210

⁸ SEWING MACHINES 84521019

⁹ SEWING MACHINES 84521029

¹⁰ GREY 52051210

District	Year	1	2	3
Rupnagar	2021-22	Farm machine parts (11.6%)	Tractors (7.7%)	Gypsum (7.0%)
	2022-23	Farm machine parts (19.8%)	Tractors (18.7%)	Whiskey (10.0%)
	2023-24	Tractors (27.6%)	Farm machine parts (11.0%)	Whiskey (10.6%)
SAS Nagar	2021-22	Meat (12.1%)	Antibiotics (7.8%)	Medicines (7.4%)
	2022-23	Meat (13.0%)	Antibiotics (10.5%)	Medicines (9.6%)
	2023-24	Meat (15.3%)	Antibiotics (9.8%)	Linen (6.2%)
Sangrur	2021-22	Basmati rice (29.0%)	Cotton ¹¹ (9.6%)	Honey (7.9%)
	2022-23	Basmati rice (43.8%)	Honey (9.6%)	Fatty acids (5.0%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (20.1%)	Honey (13.7%)	Edible oils (6.4%)
SBS Nagar	2021-22	Amoxicillin (29.0%)	Polypropylene sheets (24.1%)	Medicines (22.4%)
	2022-23	Amoxicillin (34.2%)	Polypropylene sheets (18.9%)	Medicines (18.8%)
	2023-24	Amoxicillin (39.1%)	Medicines (16.4%)	Polypropylene sheets (15.7%)
Tarn Taran	2021-22	Basmati rice (63.0%)	Broken rice (31.8%)	Rice (1.4%)
	2022-23	Basmati rice (81.6%)	Broken rice (7.9%)	Rice (6.1%)
	2023-24	Basmati rice (90.9%)	Broken rice (3.0%)	Rice (2.4%)

Source: Ministry of Commerce, Government of India

¹¹ GREY 52052310

The overall pattern underscores the need for regional diversification, district-level logistics investments, and sector-specific industrial development to broaden the state's export base beyond traditional hubs.

Building on this concentration pattern, the analysis now shifts to district-level specialisation to examine sectoral dynamics shaping Punjab exports. The data reveal three broad archetypes: (i) rice-belt districts, where basmati rice dominates the export basket; (ii) cotton-belt districts, which are either diversifying into new value chains or reinforcing their traditional textile base; and (iii) industrial clusters, characterised by strong concentrations in engineering goods, auto components, tractors, pharmaceuticals, and meat processing.

This spatial-specialisation pattern highlights the interplay between district-level strengths and the overall state export composition. While the rice belt continues to anchor agricultural exports, particularly basmati rice, industrial districts such as Ludhiana, Jalandhar, Kapurthala, and Hoshiarpur drive the state's dominance in engineering goods. S.A.S. Nagar and S.B.S. Nagar contribute significantly through pharmaceuticals, IT/ITeS, and food processing, creating pockets of high-value export activity. Cotton districts, by contrast, display mixed trajectories, with some reinforcing traditional textile activities while others explore new value chains.

Consequently, the aggregate export profile of Punjab reflects a tilt toward engineering and high-value industrial products, even as southwestern districts maintain a predominantly agriculture-based export basket. This duality underscores the need for targeted policies that consolidate strengths in high-value sectors while promoting infrastructure, diversification, and capacity-building in agriculturally dominated districts to ensure balanced, sustainable growth across the state.

The district-level export analysis of Punjab reveals distinct patterns of concentration and specialisation, highlighting both opportunities and vulnerabilities. *Table 5* presents concentration metrics, including top-1 and top-3 product shares (from *Table 4*), while *Table 6* identifies the actual products shaping these patterns, allowing for a holistic understanding of district-level export dynamics.

A group of districts exhibits high concentration around a single commodity, particularly basmati rice, demonstrating scale but also elevated risk. Fazilka, Ferozepur, Tarn Taran, and Moga show top-1 commodity shares between 72 and 88 percent, with increases over 2021–24 (*Table 5*), while *Table 6* confirms basmati rice as the dominant export in these districts, with near-total dominance in Fazilka (70 percent to 99 percent) and Ferozepur (86 percent to 94

Table 5: District wise average product share (2021-24)

District	Avg top-1 share	Top-1 share change	Avg concentration (Top 3)
Amritsar	53.2	12.6	59.3
Barnala	46.13	-5.68	70.29
Bathinda	33.03	-2.80	67.67
Faridkot	43.63	13.66	68.97
Fatehgarh Sahib	13.68	-4.75	30.25
Fazilka	88.59	28.77	97.20
Firozpur	88.36	7.67	96.03
Gurdaspur	30.72	24.34	62.59
Hoshiarpur	41.25	3.97	73.98
Jalandhar	10.64	-2.39	23.79
Kapurthala	56.73	34.67	77.70
Ludhiana	6.25	0.35	14.82
Mansa	38.22	40.75	60.47
Moga	72.1	17.82	85.75
Muktsar	31.30	-33.87	61.80
Pathankot	31.01	38.61	57.61
Patiala	11.75	-5.57	29.10
Rupnagar	19.64	16.03	41.33
SAS Nagar	13.44	3.23	30.54
Sangrur	30.98	-8.87	48.36
SBS Nagar	34.1	10.04	72.80
TarnTaran	78.52	27.92	96.06

Source: Calculated using data from Ministry of Commerce and Industry

percent). These districts’ focus on a single product exposes them to price fluctuations, international trade measures, and other external shocks. Kapurthala, although showing high top-1 concentration (57 percent), differs from rice-centric districts by exhibiting industrial upgrading; vehicle parts expanded from 39 percent to 74 percent while broadening the product basket to include a wider range of components (*Table 6*).

Table 6: District-wise top products

Amritsar	Basmati rice share climbed from 46 percent to 59 percent with other products steadily shrinking.
Barnala	Textile with 42-48 percent and pharmaceuticals with 11-23 percent make a moderately concentrated mix.
Bathinda	Cotton (all variants) remains the top three items across years.
Faridkot	Basmati share climbed from 38 percent to 52 percent with rice-cotton.
Fatehgarh Sahib	Anchored in rolling-mill parts, biscuits and baby garments.
Fazilka	Basmati share jumped from 70 percent to 99 percent with other items virtually disappearing.
Ferozepur	Basmati share jumped from 86 percent to 94 percent, with parboiled rice as the next best commodity.
Gurdaspur	Gurdaspur's exports have become increasingly rice-driven, with basmati rising from 15 percent to 39 percent.
Hoshiarpur	Tractors (37-75 kw) hold approximately 40 percent and the category label broadens in 2023-24 (other tractors).
Jalandhar	Hand tools and construction tooling dominate, contributing nearly 12 percent and 9 percent, respectively.
Kapurthala	Vehicle parts surge as the top item from 39 percent to 74 percent. Rising value addition as the basket broadens from axles to a wider parts portfolio.
Ludhiana	Vehicle parts are the top product but hold only 6 to 7 percent of the district exports, followed by scaffolding props and fasteners.
Mansa	Shift from cotton which had a share of 22-29 percent to iron and steel beams having a share of 63 percent by 2023-24.
Moga	Basmati share rose from 64 percent to 82 percent along with parboiled rice and vestiges of value added foods.
Sri Muktsar Sahib	Cotton has fallen from 51 percent to 17 percent while medicines and paper rise.
Pathankot	Pathankot's exports shifted from sewing machines to packaging goods and alcohol, now dominating the basket.
Patiala	A diverse mix of meat, metal sheets, batteries, cotton, and honey. Interestingly, honey showed a dip from 12 percent to 6.5 percent.
Rupnagar	Farm machines and tractors cumulatively make approximately 37 percent of the exports, followed by a 10 percent share of whiskey.
S.A.S Nagar	Meat processing holds the top slot with improvement from 12 percent to 15 percent. This is followed by medicines and small textiles.
Sangrur	Basmati share surged from 29 percent to 44 percent and then dropped to 20 percent, while honey showed positive growth from 8 percent to 14 percent.
S.B.S Nagar	Pharmaceutical export increased from 29 percent to 39 percent with medicines and polypropylene sheets production growing.
Tarn Taran	Basmati intensifies from 63 percent to 91 percent, while broken /non-basmati rice fades. The basket is extremely concentrated.

Source: Insights derived from data from Ministry of Commerce and Industry

Moderately concentrated districts, such as Barnala, Faridkot, S.B.S. Nagar, and Hoshiarpur, reveal stronger specialisation in pharmaceuticals, engineering, and textiles. Mansa demonstrates a dramatic shift, with steel beams supplanting cotton as the leading export (38 percent to 63 percent), while Muktsar and Sangrur show de-concentration trends, diversifying across multiple products (*Table 6*). Amritsar, Patiala, and Sangrur occupy a mid-tier range, balancing agricultural commodities, processed foods, and small-scale manufacturing, providing opportunities for targeted interventions.

Broadly diversified districts, led by Ludhiana, exhibit exceptionally low top-1 and top-3 shares 6.3 percent and 14.8 percent, respectively, reflecting a wide-ranging industrial base that includes engineering goods, machinery, and ancillary manufacturing. Jalandhar, Patiala, S.A.S. Nagar, Fatehgarh Sahib, and Rupnagar also demonstrate resilience through multiple medium-scale export lines, suggesting the capacity for further sectoral expansion and value addition.

The combined insights of these two tables indicate that Punjab's export strategy should balance scale with sophistication. Districts with high single-product dependence, such as Ferozepur, Faridkot, and Fazilka, require risk mitigation through product diversification, cultivar improvements, and GI-based branding. Ludhiana can leverage its diversified industrial base to advance up the value chain in precision engineering through testing, certification, design centres, and supplier development, drawing neighbouring low-share districts into its ecosystem. S.A.S. Nagar, with IT/ITeS, pharmaceuticals, and food-processing clusters, can consolidate competitiveness through digital manufacturing, R&D, and export-oriented infrastructure. Mid-tier districts, including Amritsar, Patiala, and Sangrur, benefit from tailored export promotion plans under a 'District as Export Hub' framework to unlock latent strengths.

Taken together, export strategy of Punjab must achieve both scale and sophistication: advancing design and intellectual property, enabling digital manufacturing, ensuring green compliance, and broadening export baskets without over-concentration. This integrated district-level approach can enhance resilience, diversify risk, and increase margins, creating a robust and sustainable export ecosystem across the state.

Which are the major dry ports for agricultural export?

Punjab emerged as a modern export hub beginning in 2005–06, with foundational developments including inland container depots (ICDs), upgraded rail and road border

infrastructure, and the launch of key food export lines. These initiatives established structured export logistics, connecting industrial and agri-food production centres to global markets.

ICD Ludhiana, inaugurated in 2005–06, became the first purpose-built container hub in the state. Initially focused on cereal preparations, the facility rapidly expanded to handle 28 products, including basmati rice and honey. Over two decades, Ludhiana functioned as Punjab anchor gateway, supporting bulk agricultural commodities and light-to-heavy engineering exports, backed by deep freight services and reliable rail connections to seaports (*Table 7*).

Amritsar Railway Station (2005–06) played an early role as a rail export hub. Active for over 15 years, it handled 15 products, including seeds, onions, and perishables. The station recorded a notable ramp-up in seed exports around 2007–08, reflecting bulk yet packaged agricultural consignments suitable for rail transport to northern borders and ports.

ICD/CFS Jalandhar and ICD Chheharta (Amritsar) specialised in basmati rice exports. ICD Jalandhar remained active for 17 years, primarily during 2005–2010, while CFS Chheharta operated for over 12 years with 5–6 products, later seeing redistribution of volumes to newer ICDs with higher capacity and better train paths.

ICD CFS Bathinda focused on dairy products, including ghee, butter oil, and milk powder, leveraging local cooperative and private dairying strength. The facility reported no activity after 2009–10. Attari Road and Rail became important for fresh vegetables, especially onions, and operated actively for 16 years with 6–8 products. Its prominence peaked between 2007–2013, aligning with border trade, and moderated due to geopolitical shifts while remaining vital for select perishables.

Between 2011–16, export infrastructure diversified. Rajasansi (Amritsar) Airport (2011–12) and ACC Amritsar (2014–15) began handling fresh and processed perishables. Although cargo volumes remained consistent, these air gateways created time-sensitive corridors for fruits, vegetables, flowers, and specialty foods, offering potential for future pharmaceutical and biologics exports with upgraded cold-chain and screening facilities. ICD CFS Amritsar briefly served as a guar gum export hub, indicating early agri-industrial diversification.

Post-2015, Ludhiana evolved into a multi-ICD cluster. Kanech (Inlogistics, 2015–16) managed cereal preparations and honey, Dhandari Kalan (PSWC, 2016–17) added jaggery, honey, and miscellaneous products, and Sahnewal (GRFL, 2016–17) handled alcoholic beverages, cereals, and basmati rice over eight years. Chowpayal (2016–17) expanded with cereals, basmati, honey, and dairy, supporting SME exporters and easing yard congestion.

Collectively, these Ludhiana ICDs improved first-mile logistics, storage competition, and container availability. Specialised export corridors emerged simultaneously. CFS Dappar (Derabassi, 2008–09) developed a buffalo meat export ecosystem with veterinary, cold-chain, and compliance capabilities.

From 2020–24, new ICDs enhanced capacity and product diversity. HTPL Kila Raipur (2020–21) and Adani ICD Kila Raipur (2021–22) handled basmati, cereal preparations, honey, beverages, and non-basmati rice. PLIL ICD (2024–25) began with basmati, honey, and non-basmati rice, demonstrating nascent decentralisation of container capacity.

Ludhiana now functions as a multi-ICD logistics ecosystem. Facilities including Chowpayal, Sahnewal, Kanech, and Kila Raipur reduce single-point risks, shorten first-mile hauls, and increase competition in stuffing, storage, and rail scheduling. Product corridors exist for basmati, cereal preparations, and honey in Ludhiana; dairy in Bathinda; meat in Derabassi; guar in Amritsar; and onions and vegetables at Attari. Air gateways remain strategic for high-value perishables and potential pharmaceutical exports, while border gateways operate cyclically. The state currently has a [presence](#) of 2 Air Cargo Complexes (ACC): Shaheed Bhagat Singh International Airport, Chandigarh; and Sri Guru Ram Dass Jee International Airport, Amritsar. Amid this, the new Halwara airport in Ludhiana will be a much needed enhancement to this capacity of air cargo logistics in the state.

To enhance Punjab export logistics, the state could co-invest and provide incentives for private cargo operators, including development of pharma-grade cold rooms at Rajasansi/ACC, establishment of GI branding and export support facilities at Fazilka, Ferozepur, Tarn Taran, and Moga, and targeted cluster promotion at ICD Kila Raipur to facilitate non-basmati rice exports. Additionally, ICD procurement data can be leveraged to design SME supplier upgradation programs in tooling, packaging, and compliance, with private actors delivering training and certification. As per [data](#) by Intellectual Property India, Government of India, Punjab has only two registered GI tags, one for basmati and the other for Phulkari (handicrafts). The state can leverage its export promotion from a diversified increase in GI tags targeted towards the promotion of ‘District as Export Hub’ framework.

Table 7: Exporting points in Punjab

Port	Initiation (FY)	Active yrs	Distinct products	#1 product (share)	#2 product (share)	#3 product (share)
ICD Ludhiana	2005–06	20	28	Basmati rice (70%)	Cereal preparations (18%)	Natural honey (6%)
ICD Sahnewal (GRFL)	2016–17	9	18–20	Basmati rice (45–50%)	Cereal preparations (28–32%)	Natural honey (10–15%)
ICD Chowpayal	2016–17	9	18–20	Basmati rice (78%)	Alcoholic beverages (8%)	Natural honey (7%)
HTPL Kila Raipur ICD	2020–21	5	15–17	Basmati rice (73%)	Alcoholic beverages (9%)	Cereal preparations (7%)
ADANI ICD Kila Raipur (Ludhiana)	2021–22	4	12–14	Non-basmati rice (68–70%)	Processed fruits/juices/nuts (20–22%)	Basmati rice (9–11%)
CFS/ICD Chheherta (Amritsar)	2012–13	12–13	10–12	Basmati rice (90–93%)	Non-basmati rice (3–4%)	Small processed/cereal lines (2–3%)
ACC Amritsar (Rajasansi)	2011–12	12	10–12	Processed vegetables (60–65%)	Other fresh vegetables (20–25%)	Fresh mangoes/other fresh fruit (10%)
ICD Kanech (Inlogistics)	2015–16	9–10	14–16	Cereal preparations (55–60%)	Natural honey (12–15%)	Non-basmati rice / walnuts (each 8–10%)
ICD Dhandari Kalan (PSWC)	2016–17	8–9	16–18	Miscellaneous preparations (55–60%)	Jaggery & confectionery (20–25%)	Cereal preparations (15–20%)
Amritsar Railway Station.	2005–06	15	15–18	Fruits & vegetables seeds (50–55%)	Millet (18–22%)	Groundnuts (12–18%)
Attari Road / Amritsar Road–Rail	2006–07	16	8–10	Other fresh vegetables (70–75%)	Fresh onions (15–20%)	Buffalo meat (5–8%)
ICD/CFS Jalandhar	2005–06	17	12–14	Basmati rice (80–85%)	Processed vegetables (10–12%)	Milled products (4–6%)
ICD Chheheta	2012–13	12+	5–6	Basmati rice (85–90%)	Non-basmati rice (5–7%)	Processed vegetables / cereals (2–4%)
ICD CFS Amritsar	2009–10	1	1	Guar gum (100%)	—	—
ICD CFS Bathinda	2007–08	2	1	Dairy products (100%)	—	—
CFS Dappar (Derabassi)	2008–09	4–5	5–6	Buffalo meat (90%+)	Basmati rice (3–5%)	Non-basmati rice / dairy (2–3%)
PLIL ICD Ahmedgarh	2024–25	1	3	Basmati rice (76%)	Natural honey (21%)	Non-basmati rice (3%)

Source: [APEDA](#)

Special Column: Attari Integrated Checkpost

Attari serves as India's first modern land port and the country's only legally sanctioned overland route for formal trade with Pakistan. Conditional on bilateral policy, it also functions as a conduit for Afghanistan-origin consignments. For Punjab, a landlocked state, Attari constitutes a strategically significant northern node, complementing rail-to-port flows from ICD Ludhiana and ICD Amritsar. As an integrated logistics facility—comprising customs, warehousing, inspection, and passenger/cargo terminals—it reduces first-mile transaction costs for producers in Amritsar, Tarn Taran, and Gurdaspur, while acting as a pressure-release mechanism during seaport congestion. Empirical evidence indicates that Attari's throughput is sensitive to operational conditions but demonstrates substantial latent demand for regional trade when functional.

In FY 2023–24, total trade through Attari reached 448 million USD, reflecting a significant increase from approximately 268 million USD in FY 2022–23. The port handled 6,871 cargo movements and 71,563 passenger crossings, highlighting both its operational capacity and its role as a key northern trade corridor. Imports were concentrated in Afghan-origin commodities, including dry fruits, dry dates, herbs, licorice, rock salt, gypsum, and glass, while outbound consignments from India encompassed agri-food products and light industrial goods such as soybean, chicken feed, vegetables, red chilies, plastic dana, and plastic yarn.

From a strategic and policy perspective, Attari offers Punjab a gateway to deepen trade integration with Eurasian and broader Asian markets. By investing in single-window pre-clearance for small consignments, mechanised cargo handling, and state-of-the-art warehousing, the corridor can significantly reduce transaction costs, improve reliability, and enhance competitiveness. Coupled with Punjab's strong agri-food and light manufacturing base, these interventions can transform Attari into a dynamic northern export hub, capable of facilitating high-value, time-sensitive trade. Leveraging this route would not only diversify the state's export portfolio but also strengthen regional supply chains, attract private-sector logistics investments, and position Punjab as a key player in cross-border trade flows, turning geographic constraints into a competitive advantage.

Conclusion

Punjab export performance reflects a dual narrative of latent potential and structural constraints. While the state accounts for a relatively small share of India's overall exports, it demonstrates strong sectoral capabilities in engineering goods, textiles, agriculture, and emerging services. District-level analysis highlights industrial diversity as a key strength, with Ludhiana, S.A.S. Nagar, and Amritsar anchoring high-value sectors, while mid-tier districts present significant scope for targeted upgradation of export products. Strengthening infrastructure at dry ports, inland container depots, and logistics corridors is central to unlocking regional growth potential.

The Attari corridor exemplifies the strategic importance of risk-aware operations and contingency planning, given its capacity to handle substantial trade flows when operational. At the policy level, Punjab export strategy must pursue both scale and sophistication, integrating advanced design, intellectual property, and digital manufacturing into industrial clusters. Concurrently, promoting technology adoption in agriculture can enhance productivity and expand exportable surpluses. Priority should be given to identifying high-value goods through systematic cost discovery, thereby aligning production incentives with productivity gains.

The state export vision must focus on transforming districts into globally integrated hubs, underpinned by product-specific supply chains and export plans. Regulatory and policy frameworks should be calibrated to support enterprises producing strategically important products. Non-fiscal incentives, including regulatory facilitation, can encourage specialisation without imposing fiscal burdens, enabling entrepreneurs and financiers to pursue market-driven growth with minimal government intervention.

References

Books & Book Chapters

- Chandra, R. (2022). Paul Krugman, new trade theory and new economic geography. In A. Pyka & M. da Graca Derengowski Fonseca (Eds.), *Endogenous growth in historical perspective* (pp. 221–249). Springer. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356538520_Paul_Krugman_New_Trade_Theory_and_New_Economic_Geography
- Horvat, B. (1999). The Heckscher–Ohlin theory. In *The theory of international trade* (pp. 45–72). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780333983386_3
- Milberg, W. (2002). The triumph of what (and whose) capitalism? In J. Michie (Ed.), *Globalization, growth, and governance: Creating an innovative economy* (pp. 45–72). Palgrave Macmillan. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1057/9780333983386_3
- Ricardo, D. (1817). *On the principles of political economy and taxation*. John Murray. <https://competitionandappropriation.econ.ucla.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/95/1970/01/Principles-of-Political-Economy-and-Taxation-1817.pdf>

Government Reports

- Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA). (n.d.). *APEDA official portal*. Government of India. <https://apeda.gov.in/>
- Directorate General of Foreign Trade, Government of India. (2020). *NIRYAT: National Import-Export Record for Yearly Analysis of Trade (2019–2020)*. https://niryat.gov.in/india#?start_date=201904&end_date=202003&default_table=default&sort_table=export_achieved-sort-desc&state_code=14
- Directorate General of Foreign Trade, Government of India. (2024). *NIRYAT: National Import-Export Record for Yearly Analysis of Trade (2023–2024)*. https://niryat.gov.in/india#?start_date=202304&end_date=202403&default_table=default&sort_table=export_achieved-sort-desc
- Directorate General of Foreign Trade, Government of India. (2024). *NIRYAT: National Import-Export Record for Yearly Analysis of Trade (2024–2025)*. Retrieved October 5, 2025, from https://niryat.gov.in/india#?start_date=202404&end_date=202503&default_table=default&sort_table=export_achieved-sort-desc&state_code=14
- Government of India. (2022). *National Logistics Policy*. India.gov.in. <https://www.india.gov.in/national-logistics-policy?page=1>
- NITI Aayog. (2020). *Export Preparedness Index 2020*. Government of India. https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2020-08/Digital_ExportPreparednessIndex2020_0.pdf

NITI Aayog. (2022). *Export Preparedness Index 2022*. Government of India. https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2022-03/Final_EPI_Report_25032022.pdf

NITI Aayog. (2023). *Export Preparedness Index 2022 (updated)*. Government of India. https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2023-07/Export-Preparedness-Index-2022_0.pdf

Office of the Controller General of Patents, Designs and Trade Marks. (2024, July 26). *State-wise registered Geographical Indications (GIs) of India*. Intellectual Property India. https://ipindia.gov.in/writereaddata/Portal/Images/pdf/State_wise_Registered_GI_of_India_26_07_2024.pdf

Press Information Bureau. (2024). *Government announces new measures to boost exports*. Government of India. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2115413>

World Bank. (2020). *World Development Report 2020: Trading for development in the age of global value chains*. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/wdr2020>

Organisational Reports

Asian Development Bank. (2019). *India's exports of services and non-tariff barriers: A trade study*. ADB. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/559296/india-exports-nontariff-barriers-trade-study.pdf>

Federation of Indian Export Organisations (FIEO). (2024). *Punjab export profile 2024*. https://fieo.org/uploads/files/file/Punjab_2024.pdf

News Articles

Arora, A. (2018, January 22). In IT exports, Mohali beats rest of Punjab. *The Times of India*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chandigarh/in-it-exports-mohali-beats-rest-of-punjab/articleshow/62600202.cms>

Hindustan Times. (2024, May 9). *Ludhiana: Bidding for airline operations in Halwara to begin soon, says Bittu*. *Hindustan Times*. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/chandigarh-news/ludhiana-bidding-for-airline-operations-in-halwara-to-begin-soon-says-bittu-101735322243095.html>

The Tribune. (2023, September 15). New high for tricity's software export. *The Tribune, India*. <https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/chandigarh/new-high-for-tricitys-software-export-598069/>

Times of India. (2024, March 2). US tariff crisis puts Punjab basmati exporters, growers in peril. *The Times of India*. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chandigarh/us-tariff-crisis-puts-punjab-basmati-exporters-growers-in-peril/articleshow/123194507.cms>

AI Disclosure

Artificial intelligence used only for rectifying orthographic errors.

Disclaimer

Due to the unavailability of a complete commodity-wise export dataset of the year 2024-25 only the data between 2017-18 and 2023-24 has been considered for an accurate comparison.

PANJ Foundation is a research think-tank based out of Punjab, India. Established in February 2024, it is registered as a not-for-profit under Section 8 of the Companies Act. PANJ operates as an independent research think-tank, providing research-based inputs and consultations to ensure socio-economic growth of Punjab. PANJ works as a collaborative front for initiating institutional and policy reform in the state of Punjab. We use our connection and familiarity with the lands of Punjab to inform reforms that ensure greatest benefits for its citizens. Through research, we aim at informing policy and institutional reform recommendations.

PANJ

*Policy Advisory and
Network for Joint Progress*

info@panj.org.in | [panjfoundation](#) | PANJ Foundation

WWW.PANJ.ORG.IN | SAS NAGAR, MOHALI, PUNJAB

© PANJ FOUNDATION 2025